

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE FEAR OF CONTRACTING CORONAVIRUS AND THE HOLIDAY PURCHASE INTENTION OF EMPLOYEES WORKING IN PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

The current study aims to determine the relationship between the fear of contracting the coronavirus, the uncertainty levels related to the coronavirus, the anxiety levels related to the coronavirus and the holiday purchase intention of the employees working in public institutions. To achieve this goal, 372 employees from Social Security Institution of Ankara were contacted, and data was collected using a survey technique. The model built within the scope of the research was tested using the partial least squares (PLS) approach. According to the findings of the research, public employees' fear of contracting the coronavirus is strongly impacted by both their uncertainty about the coronavirus and their anxiety level about the coronavirus, whereas their purchase intentions are only adversely affected negatively by their anxiety levels about the coronavirus.

Keywords: Covid 19; Fear of Contracting Coronavirus; Holiday Purchase Intention.

A RELAÇÃO ENTRE O MEDO DE CONTRATAR CORONAVIRUS E A INTENÇÃO DE COMPRA DE FERIADOS DE COLABORADORES QUE TRABALHAM EM INSTITUIÇÕES

Resumo

O presente estudo tem como objetivo verificar a relação entre o medo de contrair o coronavírus, os níveis de incerteza relacionados ao coronavírus, os níveis de ansiedade relacionados ao coronavírus e a intenção de compra de férias dos funcionários que trabalham em instituições públicas. Para atingir este objetivo, 372 funcionários da Instituição de Segurança Social de Ancara foram contatados e os dados foram coletados por meio de uma técnica de pesquisa. O modelo construído no âmbito da pesquisa foi testado utilizando a abordagem de mínimos quadrados parciais (PLS). De acordo com os resultados da pesquisa, o medo dos funcionários públicos de contrair o coronavírus é fortemente impactado por sua incerteza sobre o coronavírus e seu nível de ansiedade em relação ao coronavírus, enquanto suas intenções de compra são afetadas negativamente apenas por seus níveis de ansiedade em relação ao coronavírus.

Palavras-chave: Covid 19; Medo de Contrair Coronavírus; Intenção de compra de feriado.

LA RELACIÓN ENTRE EL MIEDO A CONTRATAR CORONAVIRUS Y LA INTENCIÓN DE COMPRA VACACIONAL DE LOS EMPLEADOS QUE TRABAJAN EN INSTITUCIONES PÚBLICAS

Resumen

El presente estudio tiene como objetivo determinar la relación entre el miedo a contraer el coronavirus, los niveles de incertidumbre relacionados con el coronavirus, los niveles de ansiedad relacionados con el coronavirus y la intención de compra vacacional de los empleados que laboran en instituciones públicas. Para lograr este objetivo, se contactó a 372 empleados de la Institución de Seguridad Social de Ankara y se recopilaron datos mediante una técnica de encuesta. El modelo construido dentro del alcance de la investigación se probó utilizando el enfoque de mínimos cuadrados parciales (PLS). Según los hallazgos de la investigación, el miedo de los empleados públicos a contraer el coronavirus se ve fuertemente afectado tanto por su incertidumbre sobre el coronavirus como por su nivel de ansiedad por el coronavirus, mientras que sus intenciones de compra solo se ven afectadas negativamente por sus niveles de ansiedad sobre el coronavirus.

Palabras clave: COVID-19; Miedo a contraer coronavirus; Intención de compra de vacaciones.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The outbreak began in Wuhan, China, and is now acknowledged as the novel type of coronavirus (Covid 19) by the World Health Organization and the Republic of Turkey's Ministry of Health. It has afflicted and has been going on to affect the entire world. The tourism industry is also one of the hardest hit by the outbreak. The most significant factors influencing this are the travel limitations imposed as part of quarantine procedures to manage and eliminate the pandemic, as well as the fact that people postpone their vacation plans for fear of getting the coronavirus.

The data and documents about the epidemic, posing a threat in the global sense, that are constantly updated and shared instantly on the official website of the Turkish Ministry of Health and the World Health Organization (WHO) were examined. With this study, researchers aimed to provide a realistic snapshot of the existing situation by highlighting the tourism sector's financial and moral losses. Owing to the fact that the world is still in the midst of the pandemic, authors attempted to develop some assumptions and recommendations regarding the future intentions of personnel working in public institutions in terms of engaging in tourism activities.

It is vital to explicitly state the fundamental problem of the research so as to clearly clarify why the study was conducted and which gap it would fill in the field of tourism or how it will contribute to the literature. Some research linked to coronavirus (Acar, 2020; Atay, 2020; Demir, Günaydın, & Demir, 2020; Ghebreyesus, 2020; İbiş, 2020; Kılıncım, 2020; Lovelace, 2020; Özkoçak, Koç, & Gültekin, 2020; Türkmen, & Özsanı, 2020; Üstün, & Özçiftçi, 2020; Ayıttey et al., 2020) and related to holiday purchase intention (Çetinkaya & Şahbaz, 2019) were discovered during the literature search undertaken for this purpose.

Following a review of these studies, it was discovered that, so far, there were no published studies on the fear of contracting coronavirus and the holiday purchase intentions of public-sector employees. As a result, it was considered that this study would be instructive. The tourism sector area has been enlarged, and public sector employees have grown more inclusive, according to the findings of the study.

From this perspective, the research question was formulated as "Does the fear of contracting coronavirus have any consequence on the intention to purchase a holiday by public-sector employees?" In this context, the current study aims to determine the relationship between the fear of contracting coronavirus and the holiday purchase intention of the personnel working in public institutions.

2 FEAR OF CONTRACTING CORONAVIRUS AND HOLIDAY PURCHASE INTENTION

"2019-nCoV" and its common name "Coronavirus", seen firstly in December 2019 in a marketplace where seafood and live animals are sold in Wuhan, China, was declared to be Covid-19 on February 11, 2020, by the World Health Organization (WHO) (Lovelace, 2020). Coronaviruses (CoV) are a broad family of viruses that cause illnesses ranging from the common cold to even more chronic complications like Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS-CoV) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) (SARS-CoV) (UNWTO, 2020). In humans, the novel kind of coronavirus, nowadays called as covid-19, causes infections in the respiratory and gastrointestinal systems.

According to the WHO investigation, all segments of society must collaborate in public health norms and social measures, and a global attempt should be made to reduce or stop the spread of Covid-19 (World Health Organization, 2020). Because the rapid growth of the Covid 19 outbreak cannot be stopped and it is unclear when the virus will be eradicated, countries are being forced to take preventative measures. Defined as a method of social isolation, the quarantine comes out at the beginning of these measures. A curfew has been established as part of the quarantine to prevent people from avoiding close contact with those around them. Curfews are used in numerous countries around the world, just as they are in ours. People stay at home and provide protection against the outbreak as a result of these restrictions.

The number of coronavirus cases worldwide has surpassed 2 million, and the number of persons who have died as a result of the Covid-19 disease has exceeded 200 thousand. The World Health Organization (WHO) named the coronavirus-induced Covid-19 disease, which is endangering the entire planet, a "pandemic," which indicates a global epidemic, on March 11, 2020 (Ghebreyesus, 2020; Cucinotta, & Vanelli, 2020). The global epidemic quickly expanded from China and other Far Eastern countries to other Asian, European, American, and African countries.

Epidemics are a severe threat to the global population as well as the global economy. The economic loss has the potential to generate economic instability. Direct costs, long-term strain, and indirect costs really do have a consequence. The Ebola epidemic, for example, has had a major impact on the economy in West Africa. The direct cost of the Ebola epidemic in Sierra Leone was estimated to be \$6 billion in 2015, including hospital costs, labor costs, and medical supply costs (Gostin, & Friedman, 2015).

According to Swarbrooke and Horner (2007), it is possible to interpret that holiday purchase decisions can be grouped under two headings as tourist-related factors and factors unrelated to tourists. While tourist-related factors are handled as "personal motivation, expendable income, health, hobbies and interests, lifestyle, attitudes, ideas and perceptions", factors unrelated to the tourist such as "availability of suitable products, advice from travel agents, friends and family members, travel restrictions, destination-related health issues, and vaccination requirements" can be cited as examples.

Starting with this, it can be said that, while the intention to purchase a holiday is considered an internal effect, the fear of contracting coronavirus has a considerable influence on health problems caused by sources other than the tourist. According to this, H1 hypothesis was developed as "Fear of contracting the coronavirus negatively and significantly affects individuals' holiday purchase intentions."

Events that are followed with great interest on a global scale, providing a significant flow of visitors to the regions where they are held and having an income-generating effect in the host countries or the attractions that destinations have that make them unique create a positive effect on the revenues obtained from the tourism sector (Karakuş & Çoban, 2018).

However, a number of unanticipated and undesirable incidents, such as acts of terrorism, political events, and epidemics, have negative consequences for the tourism industry, such as changing global travel plans, canceling reservations, and closing the country's borders to citizens from countries where the epidemic is available (Bayraktaroğlu et al., 2021).

Epidemics, which are among the most unpredictable events, erode confidence in the region where they originate (Çeti, & Ünlüönen, 2019, pp. 109-110). The tourism sector, in terms of demand, is a social event in which people travel to regions where they feel comfortable. The coronavirus outbreak, on the other hand, can cause psychological problems such as despair, anxiety, and tension, making people feel unsafe (Şeker, 2022).

According to this, H2 hypothesis was developed as "Fear of contracting coronavirus positively and significantly affects individuals' anxiety levels about coronavirus." and H3 hypothesis was produced as "Fear of contracting the coronavirus positively and significantly affects individuals' uncertainty about the coronavirus."

Depression is a mental illness that affects people's mood states. A mood state is when an individual is in a joyful, sad, troubled, overflowing, or depressed mood for a period of time. Sensation refers to an individual's ability to respond to stimuli, thoughts,

environmental, and personal circumstances with sensory responses including joy, sadness, resentment, anger, distress, and happiness.

Affective disorders develop when a certain emotional state is excessive and lasts for a long time, leading to depression. According to the World Health Organization, depression ranks the fourth among the diseases that cause physical, social, economic and emotional problems (Yıldırım et al., 2015, pp. 33).

Therefore, prevention and treatment of depression are extremely important in terms of individual and public health. In this perspective, the tourism industry plays a critical role in the prevention and treatment of depression.

Uncertainty in the tourism industry produces a risk, which leads to a crisis. A tourism crisis arises when a country's tourism sector or some of its businesses experience severe losses as a result of unmanageable natural disasters, socio-economic changes, terrorism and conflict, incorrect policies or management errors, and even face bankruptcy, and can be characterized as a situation in which a new structure of the organization seeks to address these concerns (Koç & Villi, 2021).

On the other side, crisis management refers to the process of implementing the appropriate policies and taking the necessary steps to eliminate the losses with the least amount of damage (Yakut Aymankuy, 2001). Uncertainty is the most prominent feature that makes it difficult for people to make judgments in times of crisis. A correlation can be established between people's holiday purchase intention and eliminating this ambiguity.

According to this, H4 hypothesis was formed as "Anxiety levels related to the coronavirus negatively and significantly affect the holiday purchase intentions of individuals." And H5 hypothesis was constructed as "Uncertainty levels related to the coronavirus negatively and significantly affect holiday purchase intentions of individuals." In line with the indicated hypotheses, the research model shown in Figure 1 was created.

Figure 1: Research model
Source: own elaboration

Table 1: Description of construct

Construct	Description
Motivation of the study	The anxiety, fear, stress and nausea caused by the coronavirus epidemic have deeply affected both individuals and organizations, especially the sociological and psychological problems experienced at the individual and societal level, and the economic difficulties faced by businesses and its reflection on people have increased the effects of the epidemic (Onat et al., 2021). Dugas et al. (2001) defined situations where the probability of events to occur is unknown as uncertainty and emphasized that anxiety and stress will occur if uncertainty continues. In this context, the fear, uncertainty and anxiety caused by the coronavirus are discussed in this study, taking into account the researches that people's holiday purchase intentions will be adversely affected due to the coronavirus epidemic.
Fear of contracting coronavirus	Fear of contracting the coronavirus refers to the level of fear that individuals create in them against the possibility of contracting the coronavirus.
uncertainty about the coronavirus	Uncertainty levels regarding the coronavirus express the impact of the probability of individuals not catching the coronavirus on them.
anxiety about the coronavirus	Anxiety levels about coronavirus refer to the degree to which individuals' probability of contracting coronavirus affects them.
Holiday Purchase Intention	Holiday purchase intention represents an individual's positive tendency to purchase a holiday.

Source: Own elaboration.

In order to understand the relationship between the fear of contracting the coronavirus and the intention to purchase a holiday of the personnel working in public institutions, the Planned Behavior Theory (PBT), which is frequently used in consumer behavior studies and whose validity has been determined by many studies (e.g. Han, 2021; Rahmafritria et al., 2021). PBT is a widely used theory for measuring attitudes.

According to PBT, the stronger the individual's intention to act, the higher his performance should be (Ajzen, 1991). This theory offers a model developed to predict the antecedents of people's purchase intentions. PBT provides a good framework for conceptualizing, measuring, and empirically identifying the factors that determine behavior and behavioral intentions. From this point of view, the

expressions measured within the scope of the research are shown in the table 1.

3 METHODOLOGY

Employees at the Ankara Social Security Institution were the respondents of this study. The participants were sent out the link to the Google forms-created questionnaire via various social media tools (e.g. WhatsApp, Instagram and Facebook).

Data was collected using a questionnaire form. The questionnaire is divided into two sections. The first section includes demographic and descriptive data. Fear of contracting coronavirus, uncertainty about coronavirus, anxiety about coronavirus, and holiday purchase intention are all represented in the following part. In order to measure the fear of contracting coronavirus, uncertainty levels connected to the coronavirus, and anxiety levels related to the coronavirus, the investigation by Bakioğlu, Korkmaz, and Ercan (2020) was used, while the study by Pavlou and Gefen (2004) was used to measure purchase intention.

The holiday purchase intention was measured with three expressions, while five expressions were used to assess fear of contracting coronavirus. The level of uncertainty about the coronavirus and the level of anxiety about the coronavirus, on the other hand, were measured with one expression each. The expressions were encoded using a five-point Likert scale and were arranged as 1: Strongly Disagree – 5: Strongly Agree.

The survey was posted on social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and others) to reach a broader audience and make it easier for them to access. The survey data were obtained between February 13th and March 10th, 2021. The convenience sampling method was employed to collect data in this study. This strategy is based on including everyone who responds to the questionnaire in the sample. As a result, everybody who can be reached and wants to fill out the questionnaire will be able to do so (Coşkun et al., 2015: 142).

The partial least squares (PLS-SEM) approach of structural equation modeling has been used to test the model developed in the study. PLS-SEM is a better analytical technique to use when validating models with a small sample size (Hair et al., 2014) and PLS-SEM is an iterative method for estimating structural equation modeling that does not impose distributional assumptions on the data (Fornell et al., 1996). As a result, PLS-SEM was adopted to examine the model. The SmartPLS package program has been used to evaluate PLS-SEM (Ringle, Wende, and Becker, 2015).

Table 2: Measurement items

Concept	Author	Question generated	Objective of the question
Fear of contracting coronavirus	Bakioğlu et al., 2020	I am very afraid of coronavirus (Covid-19). Thinking about coronavirus bothers me. When I think of coronavirus, I feel hot and cold. I am afraid of losing my life due to coronavirus. I get tense or worried when I see stories and news about coronavirus on social media.	Identifying tourists' fears of contracting coronavirus.
The level of uncertainty about the coronavirus	Ahorsu et al., 2020	I can't sleep because of the fear of contracting the coronavirus.	To determine the uncertainty situations of tourists due to coronavirus
Level of anxiety about the coronavirus	Ahorsu et al., 2020	I get tense or worried when I see stories and news about coronavirus on social media.	To determine the anxiety of tourists due to coronavirus
Holiday Purchase Intention	Pavlou and Gefen (2004)	If I have the opportunity in the future (in terms of time, money, etc.), I am thinking of buying a vacation. I'll probably buy a vacation in the near future. If I have the opportunity in the future (in terms of time, money, etc.), I am thinking of buying a vacation.	Determining tourists' holiday purchase intentions

Source: Own elaboration.

4 FINDINGS

The study intends to determine the relationships among the fear of contracting coronavirus, uncertainty levels regarding coronavirus, anxiety levels related to

coronavirus and holiday purchase intention of employees working in public institutions. The findings regarding the data obtained as a result of the demographic and descriptive questions are shown in the table below.

Table 1: Information by Participants' Gender, Age, Educational Status, Tenure of Service in the Public Institution

Gender	N	%	Tenure of Service in Public Institution	N	%
Male	198	53,2	Less than 1 year	33	8,9
Female	174	46,8	Between 1-5 years	98	26,3
Total	372	100	Between 6-10 years	98	26,3
Educational Status			Between 11-15 years	61	16,4
Primary School	4	1,1	16 years and more	82	22,0
High School	42	11,3	Total	372	100
Associate Degree	76	20,4	Tourism Education		
B.A. Degree	191	51,3	Yes	63	16,9
Postgraduate	59	15,9	No	309	83,1
Total	372	100	Total	372	100
Age			Tenure of Service in Tourism		
0 and less	16	4,3	No	330	88,7
Between 21-30	103	27,7	Between 1-2 years	12	3,2
Between 31-40	149	40,1	Between 2-3 years	7	1,9
Between 41-50	69	18,5	3 years and more	23	6,2
51 and over	35	9,4	Total	372	100
Total	372	100			

Source: Own elaboration.

As per the demographic data gathered, male participants (198 people) outnumbered female participants (174 people), and male participants made up 53.2 percent of the research. When the respondents' educational backgrounds were reviewed, it was discovered that the largest part of the participants were B.A. graduates, with 191 (51.3%), and the least number of participants were primary school graduates, with 4 (1.1%).

From this perspective, it is reasonable to conclude that the majority of employees at public institutions have earned a bachelor's degree from at least one faculty. On the other hand, when the ages of the participants in the research were examined, it was determined that the people who participated in the research the most were between the ages of 31-40.

Furthermore, it has been concluded that these people have served in public institutions for a

maximum of 1-5 years or 6-10 years. The examination of table 1 shows that most of the employees (309 people) in public institutions did not work in the tourism sector and it was concluded that they did not receive tourism education.

PLS-SEM consists of two structures, a measurement model and a structural model (Hair et al., 2014). For this reason, the measurement model and then the structural model were examined firstly. Within

the scope of the measurement model, the construct validity and reliability of the model were tested.

As a result of the data obtained in the first measurement model analysis, since the factor load of an expression belonging to the holiday purchase intention measurement was below .50, this expression was removed from the analysis and the analysis was repeated. The result of the final measurement model analysis is shown in Table2.

Table 2: Result of Measurement Model

Constructs	Expressions	Factor Load	t	CSR	AVE
Fear	I am very afraid of the coronavirus (Covid-19).	.772	26.894	.87	.57
	Thinking about the coronavirus bothers me.	.744	24.763		
	When I think of the coronavirus, my hands break out in a cold sweat.	.716	23.496		
	I am afraid of losing my life due to coronavirus.	.798	39.598		
	I can't sleep because of the fear of catching the coronavirus.	.729	21.962		
HPI	If I have the opportunity in the future (in terms of time, money, etc.),	.950	58.603	.93	.87
	I am thinking of buying a vacation.				
	I'll probably buy a vacation in the near future.				
Discriminant Validity	Uncertainty	Fear	Anxiety	HPI	
	Uncertainty				
	Fear	0,571	0,752		
	Anxiety	0,315	0,694		
	HPI	-0,120	-0,156	-0,197	0,934

HPI: Holiday Purchase Intention.

Source: Own elaboration.

As shown in Table 2, there is no finding that will cause a violation of the composite structure reliability (CSR) of the constructs (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Because the value of mean explained variance and factor loading values exceed the recommended value of .50, it may be indicated that convergent validity was also achieved (Hair et al., 2009).

In addition, it can be stated that discriminant validity is ensured since the square root of the mean

explained variance value of each construct in the measurement model exceeds the correlation between the construct and other constructs (Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

According to the values obtained in the measurement model, it can be stated that construct validity and reliability are provided. Accordingly, the second stage, the structural model, was examined.

Table 3: Results of Structural Model

Relationships	Path coefficient	t	P	confidence interval		VIF	R ²	f ²	Q ²
				2.5%	97.5%				
Fear → Uncertainty	.571	15.402	.000	.497	.640	1.000	.325	.485	.315
Fear → Anxiety	.694	23.954	.000	.637	.749	1.000	.480	.929	.471
Fear → HPI	.009	.110	.913	-.151	.162	2.629		.000	
Uncertainty → HPI	-.068	.991	.322	-.068	-.200	1.513	.035	.003	.030
Anxiety → HPI	-.182	2.419	.016	-.182	-.326	1.966		.018	

HPI: Holiday Purchase Intention. Source: Own elaboration.

The bootstrap resampling method was used to determine the t values of the path coefficients in the structural model, and the subsample value in this technique was set to 5000 as suggested (Hair et al., 2014; Henseler et al., 2009). The basic evaluation criterion in PLS models is the R²value (Henseler, Ringle, and Sinkovics, 2009).

Therefore, the R² value was examined at first. Considering the R² values, it can be stated that the anxiety and uncertainty levels of the participants about

the coronavirus are explained moderately by their fear levels about the coronavirus. Additionally, it is also seen that the anxiety ($\beta=.694$, $t=23.954$, $p=.000$) and uncertainty ($\beta=.571$, $t=15.402$, $p=.000$) levels of the participants about the coronavirus are positively and significantly affected by the fear levels about the coronavirus while no significant effect was found on participants' holiday purchase intentions ($\beta=.009$, $t=.110$, $p=.913$).

Accordingly, H_2 and H_3 were accepted, while H_1 was rejected. On the other hand, while the uncertainty levels of the participants regarding the coronavirus did not significantly affect their intention to purchase a holiday, the uncertainty levels of the participants regarding the coronavirus affected their anxiety levels about the coronavirus negatively and significantly ($\beta = -.182, t = 2.419, p = .016$).

Therefore, H_4 was accepted, but H_5 was rejected. According to F value, the fear levels of the participants about the coronavirus have the power to affect both their anxiety levels about the coronavirus and their uncertainty about the coronavirus at a high level (Cohen, 1988).

Table 4: Summary table of analysis categories

Theory	Data	Inference
Fear positively affects uncertainty.	Fear has a large effect on uncertainty.	Supported
Fear positively affects anxiety.	Fear has a large effect on anxiety.	Supported
Fear negatively affects HPI.	Fear does not affect HPI.	Not supported
Uncertainty negatively affects HPI.	Uncertainty does not affect HPI.	Not supported
Anxiety negatively affects HPI	Anxiety has low effect on HPI.	Supported

Source: Own elaboration.

5 CONCLUSION

The pandemic, which originated in the Chinese city of Wuhan and is now designated as the new form of coronavirus (Covid 19) by the World Health Organization and the Turkish Ministry of Health, has influenced and continues to afflict people all over the world.

The tourism industry is also one of the hardest hit by the outbreak. Undoubtedly, Travel restrictions imposed as part of quarantine procedures to manage and prevent the pandemic, as well as people delaying their travel plans for fear of contracting the coronavirus, are the principal sources for this.

The purpose of this study is to examine the fear of contracting coronavirus, the level of uncertainty about coronavirus, and the level of anxiety about coronavirus among public-sector employees, as well as the relationship between these factors and their holiday purchasing intentions.

Three hundred seventy-two employees in the Ankara Social Security Institution were approached for this purpose, and data was collected using a questionnaire method. The model built within the scope of the research was assessed using the partial least squares (PLS) approach.

According to the study's findings, public employees' fear of contracting coronavirus has a positive influence on both their uncertainty and anxiety about the virus, whereas their purchase intentions are only negatively influenced by their anxiety about the virus.

At this point, it can be asserted that anxiety levels about the coronavirus are a critical indicator of holiday purchase behavior, and that measures that reduce this level of anxiety should be prioritized.

5.1 Recommendations for Practitioners

According to World Tourism Organization statistics, there have been significant drops in tourist arrivals and tourism revenues in the tourism sector as of January 2021. The decrease had a negative impact on Turkey as well. Although the tourism sector receives support and incentives, it is difficult to entirely compensate for the losses.

The sector faces a long-term recovery period. Although medical conditions remain, it is possible that efforts carried out in the post-epidemic phase to ease the stress of the protracted quarantine and social distancing restrictions may contribute to the sector's resurrection.

Although the epidemic has macroeconomic, social, and cultural consequences for all countries throughout the world, it also has a microeconomic impact on hospitality businesses. When we look at the data of the World Tourism Organization in general, an increase has been observed in terms of both tourism revenues and the number of tourists in our country in 2019 compared to 2018.

The impact of the pandemic has resulted in a massive drop in both tourism income and the number of people traveling between June 2020 and the first half of 2021. Several national and international festivals have been pushed back till 2022.

As a result, 2022 is projected to be a busy year for the tourism industry. Businesses will need to take a number of steps in 2022 to boost their proportion of the tourism bucket. It is possible to list some of these measures:

First and foremost, employees' job safety must be assured. Those suspected of having the disease should be removed from the workplace, and necessary measures should be taken to comply with mask, distance, and hygiene standards.

Secondly, chronic patients should be separated from their workplaces or, if they must work, placed in settings where they are away from their coworkers.

Thirdly, employees' employment security should be safeguarded because the fear of losing their jobs might sometimes mitigate the coronavirus's detrimental

consequences. Since the tourism sector is a labor-intensive sector, job security of employees can positively affect their motivation and cause them to work more efficiently.

Fourth, it is conceivable to predict that, following the coronavirus, the tourism industry would switch to a highly digital era, with a period of complete isolation beginning. The robot era will begin in many regions of the world, contactless transactions will be undertaken, and social distance, hygiene, and sanitation will be prioritized, according to projections.

As a result, businesses should provide conveniences such as sterilized kitchens, disinfected transit vehicles and hotel rooms, and contactless room door cards and payments, as well as inform customers that these services are available. People will avoid being in environments where they do not feel very comfortable.

Finally, because of the coronavirus pandemic, there will be an increase in demand for masks and gloves, new technology systems in bellboy services, and contactless use in room door cards, and as a result, such developments emerge as a new marketing approach, despite the high financial cost. Instead of an all-inclusive system, an all-hygienic scheme will now be available.

All of this points to the start of a new age in tourism. Domestic tourism should be given appropriate priority in this new phase in order to significantly boost tourism potential.

5.2 Limitations

Only those working in the Ankara Social Security Institution were included in this study due to time and geographical constraints. Ankara Social Security Institution employs approximately 10.000 people, and 372 questionnaires gathered through the form were acknowledged as a constraint. In other words, the research findings can only represent the sample used in the study. As a result, future research can be carried out by incorporating individuals working in public institutions in other regions.

On the other hand, it is claimed that demographic characteristics (such as education, gender, and age) are a strong influence on consumer purchasing tendencies (Okumuş et al., 2021). The effects of demographic variables, on the other hand, were not investigated in this study. In this regard, a contribution to the literature can be made by evaluating the relationship between customers' fear of contracting coronavirus and their intention to purchase a holiday, taking into consideration the demographic factors of consumers.

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Table 5. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3	Author 4
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	x		x	x
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	x	x	x	
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	x		x	
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs		x	x	
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data		x	x	

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3	Author 4
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x	x	x	
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	x	x	x	
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse		x	x	
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x	x	x	
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	x	x	x	x
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	x	x	x	
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	x			
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	x			
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	x			

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

Processo Editorial / Editorial Process / Proceso Editorial

Editor Chefe / Editor-in-chief / Editor Jefe: PhD Thiago D. Pimentel (UFJF).

Recebido / Received / Recibido: 16.12.2021; Revisado / Revised / Revisado: 01.02.2022 – 31.03.2022 – 16.04.2022; Aprovado / Approved / Apobado: 01.06.2021; Publicado / Published / Publicado: 15.06.2022.

Seção revisada às cegas por pares / Double-blind peer review section / Sesión revisada por pares ciegos.